

WETTING AND CONSOLIDATION OF NYLON 6 POWDER COATED CARBON FIBER TOW

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SUMMARY: An attractive means for combining continuous reinforcing fibers with thermoplastic matrices entails powder coating spread fiber tows. After fusing the powder to the tow it is quenched, creating a flexible but bulky towpreg. When nylon 6 is the powder coating on carbon fiber tow, significant debulking of the towpreg occurs while the towpreg is being heated. Surprisingly, most of this debulking occurs before the nylon 6 is completely melted. For an oven setting of 260 °C the void content of a powder coated 12,000 filament tow dropped from over 90 % to under 20 % in less than 20 seconds even though the temperature inside the tow does not reach 225 °C, the final melting point of nylon 6, until 30 seconds in the oven. A capillary flow model was developed which effectively represents this wetting behavior.

KEYWORDS: nylon 6, carbon fiber, wetting, consolidation, powder coating, prepreg, towpreg, thermoplastic.

INTRODUCTION

A schematic of a powder coating process for producing flexible thermoplastic towpreg is shown in Figure 1. By spreading the multifilament tows to expose virtually all the fibers and then powder coating the exposed filaments, the difficulty of forcing molten polymer with a high viscosity into a packed bed of fibers is avoided. After powder coating the thermoplastic is melted to fuse the polymer to the fibers. The hot towpreg is quenched before the spread towpreg is condensed in order to obtain a flexible towpreg comprised of multiple plies of partially wet out fibers. Both this process and product form have been patented [1,2] and commercialized [3]. This flexible towpreg is well suited for making textile preforms by braiding and weaving

For processes like filament winding and advanced tow placement it is preferable to have a well consolidated, fully wet out, void-free towpreg with well defined dimensions. The primary objectives of this research were to develop a process as well as the attendant processing parameters to convert flexible unconsolidated towpreg into well consolidated towpreg. In earlier work on this subject [4,5] both roll consolidation and pultrusion were found to be inadequate for this task because dry fibers would hang up in the die or rollers, break, and accumulate during operation, ultimately disrupting the process. In this study non-contact heating is emphasized as a means of wetting out these dry fiber sections. Following

this thermal wetting and debulking it is possible to make well consolidated and shaped towpreg without incurring process disruptions

Fig. 1: Process for producing powder coated tow using an electrostatically charged fluidized bed

EXPERIMENTAL

The towpreg used for this research was made using 12,000 filament carbon fiber tow, Celion G30-500, from BASF and later Toray Industries. The powder coating was performed by Custom Composite Materials, Inc., now Applied Fiber Systems, Ltd [3]. The towpreg was served with nylon fiber to improve the bundle integrity. This nylon fiber was less than 1 % of the towpreg. The towpreg contained 60 % fiber by volume. The cross-sectional area of this towpreg is 8 mm² whereas the same towpreg after complete consolidation has a cross-sectional area of 0.91 mm². Thus, the flexible towpreg is quite bulky due to the incomplete melting and flow of nylon powder within the towpreg.

The apparatus for investigating wetting in an oven is shown in Figure 2. The towpreg was tied to a steel rod which was anchored at one end. The towpreg was tensioned using pressure rollers. The tension was set and measured using an ALPHACELLTM tension measuring device from Alpatron, Inc. The oven, a ThermolyneTM Type 21100 tubular furnace, was placed on rails. The oven was heated to a preset temperature while in position over the steel rod. After reaching steady state the oven was rolled over the towpreg section. The towpreg temperature was continuously recorded by computer from a thermocouple embedded in the towpreg. The experiments were repeated for different residence times, oven temperatures and towpreg tensions.

The cross-sectional areas of the towpregs were obtained from SEM at 60X magnification. The outline of the towpreg cross-section was traced using transparent paper which was then photocopied, cut and weighed. A calibration curve for the paper weight versus magnified area was used to obtain the towpreg cross-sectional area.

Fig. 2: Apparatus for studying towpreg wetting versus time, tension and oven temperature

WETTING EXPERIMENTS

Figure 3 shows the towpreg temperature and cross-sectional area for an oven setting of 260 °C. The cross-sectional area of the towpreg starts to drop rapidly once the towpreg reaches 180 °C. It stops shrinking rapidly around 20 seconds when the towpreg is at 210 °C. There is a gradual further shrinkage to about 1 mm², close to the void-free cross-sectional area of 0.91 mm².

Fig. 3: Towpreg cross-sectional area and temperature versus residence time in oven.

Similar responses were seen at oven settings of 332 and 386 °C. Due to the higher temperatures, the residence times to approach 1 mm² were reduced. Also, at 386 °C the towpregs expanded after 40 seconds due to degradation of the nylon. For all three oven settings most of the towpreg cross-sectional shrinkage occurred before the towpreg reached 225 °C, the reported melting point for nylon 6.

The rapid shrinkage still occurred with only nominal tension. Better overall reduction in void content was achieved with a tension of 4 lb_f (1.8 kg_f). Increasing tension further led to no further reduction in void content.

Since so much wetting occurred below the apparent melting point for nylon 6 sections of towpreg were videotaped in a hot stage microscope. The extent of fiber wetting started to increase around 180 °C, as in the oven experiments. Most of the wetting was completed by the time the towpreg reached 225 °C.

Figure 4 shows a DSC scan of this nylon 6 towpreg. There is evidence of melting starting near 180 °C. It is highly likely that considerable melting and recrystallization occurs in this nylon 6 at low temperatures since the towpreg is quenched extremely rapidly in production - on the order of 100 °C per second. This melting of metastable crystals is sufficient to permit substantial fiber wetting to occur before the nylon 6 recrystallizes. This virtually concurrent melting and recrystallization is not evident in Figure 4 because the latent heat effect of overlapping melting and recrystallization is virtually zero. The hot stage microscopy does support this basis for the low temperature wetting.

Fig. 4: DSC trace of towpreg melting at 10 °C/min showing melting beginning near 180 °C.

WETTING MODEL

A capillary flow model was developed for the wetting observed in the oven. The derivation of the model is presented elsewhere [6]. The area of the tow, A_{tow} , is:

$$A_{tow} = k_1 \left(\frac{\exp\left(\frac{E_a}{RT}\right)}{\left(1 - \frac{T}{k_2}\right)^{\frac{11}{9}} t} \right) \quad (1)$$

where k_1 depends on material and system properties, E_a is the activation energy for viscous flow, R is the gas constant, T is temperature, k_2 is a material constant and t is time. The constant k_1 is:

$$k_1 = N_{tow} \frac{4\sqrt{3}}{9} \left(\frac{R_m}{R_f} \right)^3 R_m^3 \left(\frac{v_{fl}}{v_{ml}} \right) \left(\frac{\eta_o}{\gamma_o \cos \theta} \right) \quad (2)$$

where the parameters in equation 2 are defined in Table 1.

Table 1 Parameters Used to Estimate k_1 in Capillary Flow Model

R_m	Particle Radius	5.5 Microns
R_f	Fiber Radius	4 Microns
θ	Contact Angle	42°
v_{fl}	Final Fiber Volume Fraction	0.6
v_{ml}	Final Matrix Volume Fraction	0.4
η_o	Viscosity of Nylon 6 at 232 °C	422 Pa•s
γ_o	Surface Tension at 0 K	264 Dyne/cm
N_{tow}	Number of Filaments in Tow	12,000

The first parameter in Table 1, R_m , is the mean particle size. The mean particle radius of the nylon 6 powder was determined to be 72 microns. However, this radius is before the powder was fused to the fiber. Furthermore, such large particles bridge multiple fibers and multiple flow channels. The approach used to obtain R_m equal to 5.5 microns is based on the initial hydraulic radius of the flow channel. Using the initial tow cross-sectional area of the towpreg of 8 mm and assuming 12,000 channels, equal to the number of filaments in the tow, a hydraulic radius was calculated for each channel, assuming each channel was equivalent in size. Then the hydraulic radius was set equal to R_m . Additional parameters in Table 1 readily determined from the initial towpreg include the number of filaments in the tow, the fiber radius, the fiber volume fraction and the matrix volume fraction. The volume fractions were calculated from the measured weight fractions assuming no voids in the fully consolidated towpreg.

No data was available for the contact angle for nylon 6 on carbon fiber. An angle of 42° was selected based on measurements for related polymers on carbon fiber [7]. The surface tension at absolute zero, γ_o , was calculated using the Guggenheim equation [8],

$$\gamma = \gamma_o \left(1 - \frac{T}{k_2} \right)^{\frac{11}{9}} \quad (3)$$

a known surface tension for nylon 6 of 35 dyne/cm at 265°C [9], and an empirical estimate of k_2 obtained by fitting equation 1 as discussed below. The viscosity, η_o , was measured by capillary viscometry at a low apparent shear rate of 46 s⁻¹.

The value of k_1 obtained using these parameters is 1.3 x 10⁻⁴ mm²•s. This value is fairly close to the empirically determined value of 3.88 x 10⁻⁵ mm²•s. The value of k_1 is very

sensitive to the choice of R_m since k_1 depends on R_m raised to the sixth power. For example, using the measured powder radius of 72 microns leads to a very high estimate of k_1 equal to $650 \text{ mm}^2 \cdot \text{s}$.

Unfortunately, the second constant, k_1 , in Equation 1 cannot be estimated in advance. Based on the Guggenheim Equation k_2 is the imaginary critical temperature of the polymer. For polymers in general, estimates of k_2 have ranged from 600 K to 900 K [8]. Thus, the value of 663 K obtained by fitting the data appears reasonable.

Figure 5 presents a simulation of A_{tow} versus time for an oven setting of 260 °C along with the experimental results. The empirically determined values of k_1 and k_2 were used in this simulation. Since the temperature of the towpreg changes while the fibers are wet out, it was necessary to use time-temperature superposition to establish equivalent incremental residence times at a reference temperature. Equation 1 was used as a basis for conducting this time-temperature superposition. Equation 4 shows the resulting expression.

Fig. 5: Simulation of towpreg cross-sectional area versus residence time in oven.

$$dt_{\text{ref}} = dt \left(\frac{k_2 - T}{k_2 - T_{\text{ref}}} \right)^{\frac{11}{9}} \exp \left(\frac{E_a}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_{\text{ref}}} - \frac{1}{T} \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

The temperature dependence of the contact angle, which is unknown, has been ignored in this superposition expression. In the simulation shown in Figure 5 the reference temperature time increments have been converted back to real time. Based on the observation of no flow below 180 °C, dt_{ref} was set equal to zero until 180 °C was attained. No further change in towpreg area was permitted once the simulation reached an area of 0.91 mm^2 , representing a void free towpreg.

The simulation shown in Figure 5 represents the experimental trends well. Once the threshold temperature of 180 °C was reached both the model and the experimental results show rapid wetting. Experimentally, complete wetting is not achieved. This discrepancy between the model and experiment is attributed to the somewhat random distribution of the powder in the towpreg, the large size distribution of the powder, and the considerable variability of the cross-sectional areas of the actual flow channels. While some flow channels have excess resin, others are starved of resin. Hence, not all the voids are removed until external pressure is applied.

CONTINUOUS CONSOLIDATION

Based on these wetting experiments a new process for converting the flexible towpreg into consolidated ribbon was developed and tested. Figure 6 presents a schematic diagram of this process. The towpreg is tensioned since this improves wetting. The oven reduces the void content of the towpreg to below 25%. The hot towpreg enters a circular die with a cross-sectional area of 1.4 mm² in order to induce some pressure driven resin flow. Then the emerging towpreg is pressed by steel rollers with a gap setting equal to the thickness sought for the ribbon. At the same time these rollers quench the towpreg.

Fig. 6: Apparatus for continuous conversion of unconsolidated powder coated tow into consolidated flat towpreg.

Processing conditions for continuous consolidation have not been optimized. Following is an example of conditions which led to a well consolidated ribbon with less than 2 % voids. The tension was set at 1.8 kg_f. The oven and die were set at 260 °C and 275 °C respectively. Samples were collected at different line speeds. Surprisingly, towpreg with the lowest void content was collected at the highest speed attempted, 6 m/min.

Since this process incorporates a die, as in pultrusion, it is informative to compare this experimental line speed with pultrusion speeds. For both thermosets and thermoplastics pultrusion speeds are typically less than 3 m/min. The high speed achieved in this trial run is quite promising. By extending the length of the oven and possibly the length of the die, successful consolidation at even higher speeds is expected.

DISCUSSION

The rapid wetting and ease of consolidation of nylon 6 coated carbon fiber towpreg may not occur in other systems. Nylon melt has a low viscosity compared to most polymer melts. Also, nylon wets and bonds to the oxidized carbon surface very well. Thus, research is in progress at Georgia Tech to examine the wetting and consolidation of other combinations of polymers and fibers.

It is common practice to ignore contributions due to wetting in analyzing the consolidation of thermoplastic composites [10]. This research clearly shows that wetting without the application of external pressure can lead to substantial debulking and reduction in void content. Frequently in processing thermoplastic composite preforms the preform is heated above its melt temperature in an oven before shaping and consolidating it in a mold below the solidification temperature of the matrix. For nylon 6 powder coated carbon fiber preforms extensive debulking of the preform occurs before the preform is inserted in the mold. Thus, these unconsolidated preforms can be molded virtually as quickly as fully consolidated sheets are stamped.

CONCLUSIONS

Nylon 6 powder coated carbon fiber tows are rapidly wet out and debulked by heating the towpreg above 180 °C. The nylon 6 behaves like a melt above 180 °C even though the final melting temperature for nylon 6 is 225 °C. By treating the nylon 6 as a melt above 180 °C a capillary flow model represents the wetting and debulking of the towpreg well. By combining an oven, die and roll consolidator in line this flexible towpreg can be converted into consolidated towpreg rapidly.

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